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Research Article

**PUBLIC AWARENESS TOWARD TUBERCULOSIS AMONG
SAUDI POPULATION, SAUDI ARABIA**

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Abstract:

Introduction: Tuberculosis (TB) is one of the most common infectious disease and cause of death worldwide. Nowadays, there is available vaccine to prevent the disease but still the developing countries are fighting this fetal disease, even though the percentage of TB has been decreased by vaccination. In Saudi Arabia, the incidence of TB is decreased dramatically which reach 12/100,000 population.

Objective: To assess the knowledge, attitude and practice towards TB among general populations in Saudi Arabia.

Method: This is a cross-sectional study with self-administered questionnaire distributed randomly among general population in Saudi Arabia in the period from January to February 2019. The sample size is 350 participants and the result will be entered and analyzed by SPSS.

Result: 350 participants filled the questionnaire. Most of participants answered the surveys correctly. Results show good level of awareness among participants. 180 (51.4%) of the participants mentioned that Bacteria is the main cause of TB. The vast majority of the participants don't know the mode of TB transmission 217 (62%). 210 (60%) participants believe that TB is very serious disease.

Conclusion: Participants shows an acceptable level of knowledge among the general population. But, there are some misconception regarding the cause and prevention of TB disease.

Keywords: tuberculosis, TB, Awareness, Saudi Arabia.

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INTRODUCTION:

Tuberculosis (TB) is an infectious disease caused by bacteria called *Mycobacterium tuberculosis*, is affecting various body organs but lungs mostly [1]. TB is one of the major causes of death worldwide many factors activate the TB such as Human Immune Deficiency Virus (HIV/AIDs), migration and the growth of populations [2]. Nowadays, there is available vaccine to prevent the disease but still the developing countries are fighting this fetal disease [3]. In Asia there are millions of cases has been recorded in 2015[4]. According to the World Health Organization (WHO) in 2016, Saudi Arabia reported an annual TB incidence rate of 12/100,000 population [5]. Even though the incidence rate of TB has been decreased in Saudi Arabia from 2000 till now, still TB in Saudi Arabia not fully controlled. The world will eradicate the incidence of TB and prevent new cases by giving the vaccination [5]. Increasing the awareness of TB disease will help in decreasing the prevalence and preventing new cases. Many studies revealed that the prevalence of TB decrease dramatically with increase public awareness. This study aimed to evaluate the level of awareness towards TB among general populations in Saudi Arabia.

Table 1: shows the demographic information of participants:

	Frequency (%)	
Gender	Male	190(54.3%)
	Female	160(45.7%)
Educational level	Did not enter school	23(6.5%)
	Primary school	41(11.7%)
	high school	196(56%)
	Bachelor	90(25.7%)
Age	20-40	278(79.5%)
	Above 40	72(20.5%)

Table 2 shows the general knowledge of included participants towards TB disease. In which 180 (51.4%) of the participants mentioned that Bacteria is the main cause of TB and 65 (18.6%) of the participants said that smoking is the cause of TB while the remaining chose winter, poor hygiene and don't know. The vast majority of the participants don't know the mode of TB transmission 217 (62%) and 114 (32.6%) believe that it transmit by coughing/sneezing droplets. Regarding the signs and symptoms of TB, the majority of the participants chose that all mentioned symptoms are correct 192 (54.9%). 53 (15.1%) participants believe that hemoptysis is symptom of TB and 30(8.6%)

METHODOLOGY:

A cross-sectional study which targeted general populations. Sample size was 350 participants which was distributed randomly in the period from January to February 2019. Self-administrated questionnaire containing two parts. First part is asking for demographic data such as Age, Gender and Educational level. The second part is evaluating the awareness and knowledge of TB. Data analysis, done by using SPSS.

RESULT:

350 participants have filled the questionnaires. The age was classified on two categories. First category was between 20-40 years old and they were the majority of participants (79.5%). Second category were above 40 years old and they were only (20.5%). Males participants were (54.3%) and females were (45.7%). Regarding the education level, more than half of participants have finished high school. Approximately, quarter of the participants have bachelor degree. (6.5%) of the participants have never been in school and (11.7%) of the participants have only finished the primary school. (table1)

participants know that fever is sign of TB. Regarding the Preventive methods of TB. Most of the participants believe that if keeping hand hygiene is preventive way 75 (21.4%) participants. 68 (19.4%) participants know if avoidance handshaking could prevent TB disease and 66 (18.9%) of the participants know if covering mouth while sneezing is preventive way. 33(9.4%) of the participants believe that isolation of TB patients will prevent spreading the disease. Only 25 participants (7.1%) know that vaccination prevent the TB. Regarding the treatment availability, most of the participants (80%) believe that TB has treatment while (20%) of the participants don't know if there is available treatment.

Table 2: shows the general knowledge of included participants (N=350):

Knowledge Assessments	Frequency	Percent %
What is the cause of TB?		
Bacteria	180	51.4
Smoking	65	18.6
Winter	38	10.9
Poor hygiene	32	9.1
I don't Know	35	10
What is the mode of transmission TB?		
Hand to hand	19	5.4
Coughing/sneezing droplets	114	32.6
I don't know	217	62
What are signs and symptoms of TB?		
Hemoptysis	53	15.1
Weight Loss	45	12.9
weakness	30	8.6
Fever	30	8.6
All are correct	192	54.9
What are preventions methods of TB?		
Keep hand hygiene	75	21.4
Avoid Handshaking	68	19.4
Cover mouth while coughing/sneezing	66	18.9
Close Windows	35	10
Isolating of TB patients	33	9.4
Vaccinations	25	7.1
I don't know	48	13.7
Is there treatment for TB?		
Yes	280	80
No	70	20

Table 3 shows the attitude and practice of included participants, 210 (60%) participants believe that TB is very serious disease while 40 (11.4%) believe that it is not serious disease, 100 (28.6%) participants don't know if TB disease is serious or not. Most common reaction of patients with TB symptoms will be fear 170 (48%) and 105 (30%) will seek health

care. 290 (83%) desire to help TB patients, about 60(17%) of participants want to stay away from TB patient. Regarding participants practice, the majority of participants believe that modern health care is the choice of TB treatment, but 90 (25%) don't know what the choice of treatment is.

Table 3: shows the attitude and practice among participants:

Attitude & Practice Assessments	Frequency	Percent %
What is your thought on seriousness of TB?		
Very serious	210	60
Not serious	40	11.4
I don't know	100	28.6
What is your reaction if you had TB symptoms?		
Fear	170	48.6
Sadness/Hopelessness	75	21.4
Visit health facility	105	30
What is your feeling about TB patients?		
Stay away from them	290	82.9
I have no exact feeling	60	17.1
What is your Choice for TB treatment?		
Modern health care	248	70.9
Inhale hot water	12	3.5
I don't know	90	25.7

DISCUSSION:

This study aimed to assess the knowledge, practice and attitude towards TB disease, and we found that there is mild to moderate awareness towards TB disease and its prevention measurements.

In contrast, study in the west of Saudi Arabia showed low level of TB awareness among Jeddah populations. More than half of participants know that bacteria is the cause of TB. Only 10% of the participants don't know the real cause of TB. Also, there is misconception among high percentage of participants about TB regarding the cause in which participants chose cold air, smoking and poor hygiene as causes of TB.

Generally, participants have acceptable level of awareness towards TB disease and the methods of prevention.

In comparison, one study done in Al-Riyadh city we found that percentage of people who don't know the cause of TB was 50% while in our study only 10%. Also, the percentage of people who know the mode of transmission 60% while in our study only 32.6%. Majority of the participants of both studies were optimistic which they believe that TB is curable with 74% and 80% respectively [6].

CONCLUSION:

Participants shows an acceptable level of knowledge among the general population. But, there are some misconception regarding the cause, prevention and

mode of transmission of TB disease

We recommend increasing the level of awareness and to fill the gap among people in Saudi Arabia by increasing campaigns.

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